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Exploring Strange New Legal Worlds: Navigating the Spectral Limits of Outer Space Treaty Interpretation in Light of the Moon Agreement

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ABSTRACT

From valuable metals and nuclear power to scientific discovery, outer space presents profitability and power for those with the means to sail its seas. Human civilization demands the natural resource exploitation of Earth and often pursues the depletion of resources with little regard for future implications, rendering space resource exploitation an inevitable desideratum. Indeed, humanity faces the choice of allowing the pernicious and boorish consumption of space resources or of upholding international law to govern space exploitation in a peaceful manner.

Five United Nations treaties dictate the proper use of space. Articles I and II of the Outer Space Treaty serve as the paramount principle within space law by affording the freedom to use space to all humankind. However, the extent of exploitation an actor may conduct remains unclear because the treaty alludes to a quasi-paradox by requiring space activities to benefit all countries, banning appropriation of space, and guaranteeing the freedom to use — commercially exploit — space. The most recent space treaty, the Moon Agreement, attempts to resolve this paradox by sanctioning lunar exploitation under the implementation of an international regime. However, the treaty lacks support from major space-faring states, rendering space a legal quagmire. I delimit Articles I and II of the Outer Space Treaty to determine the legal obligations imposed on space actors using the unaccepted overinclusive language of the Moon Agreement, concluding the Outer Space Treaty independently necessitates a regime to govern space exploitation.

KEYWORDS: space resource exploitation, Outer Space Treaty, international legal regime, Moon Agreement, freedom of use

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1. INTRODUCTION: A NOVEL APPROACH

Outer space offers vast and untapped potential: scientific knowledge, strategic positions, and extractable resources lie scattered across its expanse. As commercial and governmental actors accelerate their extraterrestrial activities, international law struggles to define the legality of resource use. Human civilization demands natural resource exploitation and often pursues the depletion of resources with little regard for future implications, rendering space resource exploitation an inevitable desideratum.² A new space race dawns as commercial space actors rise. Competing interests and unchecked ambition inevitably lead to conflict. Indeed, humanity faces the choice of allowing the pernicious consumption of space resources or of upholding international law to govern space exploitation in a peaceful manner.³

The soul of the space law constellation, the 1967 Outer Space Treaty reserves space exclusively for peaceful purposes and governs basic legal issues that may arise during space activities.⁴ Yet, the Treaty ultimately remains one of principles—lacking the overt specificity and substance required to legally justify resource exploitation with ease.⁵ It only provides a serpentine justification—containing several cumbersome caveats—for the legality of resource exploitation within Articles I and II.⁶ Indeed, Articles I and II allude to a quasi-paradox by framing space as an inclusive environment that permits exploitation of space but not appropriation.⁷ This quasi-paradox stands at the heart of modern resource law debates.⁸ The subsequent 1979 Moon Agreement attempts to resolve this tension by reiterating Outer Space Treaty principles and explicitly sanctioning lunar exploitation with implementation of a governing international regime.⁹ However, the lack of state acquiescence to the Moon Agreement renders it extraneous in practice.¹⁰

² See generally Bilder, Richard B. (2009). A Legal Regime for the Mining of Helium-3 on the Moon: US Policy Options. *Fordham International Law Journal*, 69(2), 243-299, 251; David, L. (2019). *Moon Rush: The New Space Race*. (2019). National Geographic, 156-57. Indeed, Helium-3 represents one of the most commercially profitable prospects for exploitation on the moon. *Ibid.* See also Elvis, M. et al. (2021). Concentrated Lunar Resources: Imminent Implications for Governance and Justice. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A*, 379(2188), 1-21, 2 for a thorough and scientific description of potentially valuable resources present on the moon for commercial exploitation.

³ McDougal, M.S. (1963). Enjoyment and Acquisition of Resources in Outer Space. *University of Pennsylvania Law Review* 111(5), 521-636, 539. Because “relevant resources are . . . concentrated and dispersed in many different modalities and degrees,” conflict over right to access is likely. *Ibid.*

⁴ Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, *opened for signature* Jan. 27, 1967, 18 U.S.T. 2410, 610 U.N.T.S. 205 (entered into force October 10, 1967) [hereinafter Outer Space Treaty].

⁵ Paxson, E.W. (1993). Sharing the Benefits of Outer Space Exploration: Space Law and Economic Development. *Michigan Journal of International Law*, 14(3), 487-517, 489. See also De Man, P. (2016). *Exclusive Use in an Inclusive Environment*. Springer, 79 (reasoning treaty writers left “property rights in natural resources” to “the background” in favor of resolving more pressing issues of sovereignty and peace).

⁶ Tronchetti, F. (2009). *Exploitation of Natural Resources of the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies: A Proposal for a Legal Regime*. Brill, 4 (noting the Treaty uses “general language” and omits language concerning “exploitation”).

⁷ *Ibid.* at 230.

⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹ See Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies, *opened for signature* Dec. 18, 1979, 1363 U.N.T.S. 22 (entered into force July 11, 1984) [hereinafter Moon Agreement]. See also Davis, M. E. & Lee, R. L. (1999). Twenty Years After the Moon Agreement and Its Legal Controversies. *Australian International Law Journal* 9-32, 10 (arguing the Moon Agreement “expands on the principles embraced in the Outer Space Treaty”).

¹⁰ See Paxson, *supra* note 5, at 497. Currently, parties to the Moon Agreement include Armenia, Australia, Austria, Belgium, Chile, Kazakhstan, Kuwait, Lebanon, Mexico, Morocco, Netherlands, Pakistan, Peru, Philippines, Turkey, Uruguay, and Venezuela. *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies Participant*. The United Nations Office for Disarmament Affairs. September 29, 2014, from

Consequently, the politically frail Moon Agreement and general Outer Space Treaty stalemates analysis of legal obligations imposed on space exploiters.

To escape the stalemate, this Article introduces a novel approach—spectral treaty interpretation—which situates the Outer Space Treaty along a spectrum of subsequent legal instruments. With the Moon Agreement marking the outermost ceiling of acceptable readings of the Outer Space Treaty, spectral interpretation treats subsequent, more detailed instruments as directional beacons that confine earlier, principle-heavy language without displacing it. Spectral interpretation consists of a metaphorical approach to treaty interpretation by placing legal instruments upon a spectrum—see *Figure 1*—to realize a range of possible interpretations based on the relationships between the treaty. This approach conceives treaty interpretation as a fluctuation along a spectrum, recognizing the impact of successive treaties or other contextual developments rather than focusing on a single isolated and uncontextualized instrument. Article 31 of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties provides doctrinal support for this method, instructing interpreters to read treaties considering their “context” so that *ut res magis valeat quam pereat*—legal instruments must operate, not fail.¹¹ While the Moon Agreement lacks binding authority, it still carries nuanced context for what discerning the legal obligations the Outer Space Treaty does—and does not—impose.

Spectral Treaty Interpretation

Figure 1

The idea that a later, more operational instrument calibrates rather than supplants the legal obligations of an earlier treaty already underpins two mature treaty regimes.¹² In the sea context, the 1994 Agreement

<https://treaties.unoda.org/t/moon/participants>. Saudi Arabia withdrew from the Agreement on January 5, 2024—further demonstrating the lack of enthusiasm regarding the attempt to regulate lunar resource exploitation. *Ibid.*

¹¹ United Nations Convention on the Law of Treaties, opened for signature May 23, 1969, 1155 U.N.T.S. 331 (entered into force January 27, 1980) [hereinafter Vienna Convention], Art. 31(1); Gardiner, R. (2015). *Treaty Interpretation* (2nd ed.). Oxford University Press, 179-180 (“requir[ing] a preference for an interpretation which gives a term some meaning rather than none”). Parties to the Outer Space Treaty and parties to the Moon Agreement are not identical, but that very fact provides insight into interpretation of the Outer Space Treaty. Kadelbach, S. (2018). The International Law Commission and Role of Subsequent Practice as a Means of Interpretation Under Articles 31 and 32 VCLT. *QIL Zoom In*, 46, 5-18, 8 (“Subsequent agreement must be ‘regarding the interpretation’ and the application of the treaty.”).

¹² *See ibid.* at Art. 31(3)(c) (requiring interpreters to consider “relevant rules of international law”); Agreement Relating to the Implementation of Part XI of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea of 10 December 1982, opened for signature, July 28, 1994, 1836 U.N.T.S. 3, Art. 2(1) [hereinafter Part XI Implementation Agreement]; Nagoya Protocol on Access to Genetic Resources and the Fair and Equitable Sharing of Benefits Arising from Their Utilization, opened for signature, Oct. 29, 2010, 3008 U.N.T.S. 3, Art. 4(1) [hereinafter Nagoya Protocol].

Relating to the Implementation of Part XI of United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea declares it “shall be interpreted and applied together with Part XI as a single instrument,” thereby fixing the upper limit of what the original seabed-mining articles may require.¹³ The Seabed Disputes Chamber’s 2011 advisory opinion has since treated the Agreement’s streamlined, market-oriented rules as the controlling gloss on States’ due diligence duties.¹⁴ A parallel dynamic operates in biodiversity law. Parties interpret the 1992 Convention on Biological Diversity’s open-ended promise of “fair and equitable benefit-sharing” through the procedure laid down by the 2010 Nagoya Protocol.¹⁵ The Protocol serves as a supplementary accord many States accept as the practical ceiling of their Article 15 commitments and that the EU has transposed verbatim into Regulation 511/2014.¹⁶ These analogues confirm that spectral interpretation is not an idiosyncratic innovation; it systematizes a well-established, Vienna-Convention-compliant method where later legal instruments operate as directional beacons that prevent earlier, principle-heavy treaties from being stretched beyond contemporary consensus.¹⁷ This is precisely the role the Moon Agreement can play vis-à-vis the Outer Space Treaty.

Anchoring the Outer Space Treaty’s open-textured freedoms to the Moon Agreement—however sparsely ratified—therefore reconciles commercial viability with inclusivity and supplies a principled, doctrinally orthodox pathway for regulators and courts to evaluate exploitative projects pending a comprehensive multilateral regime. If law is to govern the final frontier, its interpretive lenses must evolve as rapidly as the technologies they regulate; spectral interpretation aims to provide precisely such an adaptive lens. This Article proceeds in four parts. Section II dissects the semantic reach of Outer Space Treaty terms. Section III glosses three construals of Article I’s benefits clause and defends a positive yet flexible legal duty calibrated just short of the Moon Agreement’s equitable-sharing mandate. Sections IV and V reconceptualize Article II’s non-appropriation principle, distinguishing territorial areas from divisible resources to explain why *in-situ* resource use remains non-appropriative.

¹³ Part XI Implementation Agreement, *supra* note 12, at Art. 2(1) (“shall be interpreted and applied together with Part XI as a single instrument”).

¹⁴ *Responsibilities and Obligations of States Sponsoring Persons and Entities with Respect to Activities in the Area* (Advisory Opinion), Case No. 17, 2011 I.T.L.O.S. Rep. 10, ¶¶ 131-35 (Seabed Disputes Chamber) (applying the less onerous standards written into the 1994 Agreement’s Annex, Section 5—rather than the original, more rigid procedures of 1982 Part XI). Because ITLOS is a standing international tribunal whose opinions are widely cited, the decision supplies a persuasive comparative precedent: if courts interpret UNCLOS through its later implementing agreement, it is reasonable to interpret the Outer Space Treaty through the Moon Agreement to determine the maximum content of Articles I & II.

¹⁵ Convention on Biological Diversity Art. 15, June 5, 1992, 1760 U.N.T.S. 79 [hereinafter CBD]; Nagoya Protocol, *supra* note 12, at Pmbl., Arts. 6-7. Because Articles 6 and 7 the Nagoya Protocol spell out how the benefit-sharing principle must be carried out in practice, they are the clearest illustration of an operational layer that gives teeth to CBD Article 15—mirroring the way the Moon Agreement, arguably, operates as a ceiling setting elaboration for Outer Space Treaty Articles I and II.

¹⁶ See Regulation 511/2014, of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 Apr. 2014, Official Journal of the European Union, L 150/59 (transposing Nagoya’s procedures as the authoritative elaboration of CBD obligations despite non-universal ratification).

¹⁷ See generally Vienna Convention, *supra* note 11, at Art. 31(3)(c); Villiger, M. E. (2009). *Commentary on the 1969 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties*. Brill. 433-37 (discussing the role of subsequent agreements in interpretation).

2. THE SEMANTIC REACH OF ARTICLE I

Article I ensures three space freedoms—access, exploration, and use.¹⁸ These freedoms establish a legal framework enabling all states to carry out space activities without discrimination and provide legal justification for space exploitation. Article I additionally imposes a benefits provision by requiring “use of outer space . . . be carried out for the benefit and in the interest of all . . .”¹⁹ Undoubtedly, this language imposes a legal constraint—however vague—on a space actor’s ability to exercise exclusive control over space resources.²⁰ However, the exact scope of this legal obligation remains unclear. Spectral interpretation first asks: what is the maximum interpretation Article I can bear before it collapses into the Moon Agreement’s more exacting language? That ceiling cannot be exceeded; yet anything short of it remains potentially incompatible with the Outer Space Treaty.

2.1. Defining the Space Freedoms

The freedom to *use* space serves as the crux for *exploiting* space—commercially or otherwise. Doctrinally, *exploration* comprises an activity directed toward the improvement of knowledge but contains no “explicitly stated goal of immediate practical application.”²¹ *Use* pursues functional ends “beyond space itself,” thus *use* allows for “interests” to be “transformed into actionable goals.”²² In this context, *use* reasonably serves as a synonym of exploitation—in the context of space law.²³ Thus, exploitation of space involves the transformation of resources into value.²⁴ The Outer Space Treaty omits the term *exploitation*.

However, the Moon Agreement places the terms *use* and *exploitation* within the same conceptual framework as the Outer Space Treaty.²⁵ Article 11(5) dictates:

States Parties to this Agreement hereby undertake to establish an international regime, including appropriate procedures, to govern the exploitation of the natural resources of the Moon *as such exploitation is about to become feasible*.²⁶

Under a spectral lens, the term’s placement is decisive.²⁷ The Moon agreement presupposes that *exploitation* is a subset of *use* because the underlying right to use space already exists.²⁸ If exploitation were excluded

¹⁸ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 4, at Art. I. *See also e.g.* Larson, P.B. (2021). Is There a Legal Path to Commercial Mining on the Moon? *University of Pittsburgh Law Review*, 83(1), 1-50, 13-14 (discussing Article I’s guarantee of free lunar use); Hobe, S. and De Man, P. (2017). National Appropriation of Outer Space and State Jurisdiction to Regulate the Exploitation, Exploration and Utilization of Space Resources, *Zeitschrift für Luft-und Weltraumrecht German Journal of Air and Space Law* 66(3), 460-475, 474 (explaining the “equal interest” of all states in space”).

¹⁹ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 4, at Art. I.

²⁰ *See* Larson, *supra* note 18, at 12 (“The Moon is not free for unlimited commercial exploitation”); McDougal, *supra* note 3, at 543 (“The probabilities appear excellent that the general community will not regard many of the more important resources of space as subject to exclusive appropriation”).

²¹ De Man, *supra* note 5, at 79-80.

²² *Ibid.*, 80 (citing L. Peyrefitte. (1993). *Droit de l’espace*. Dalloz, 230; 232-33).

²³ Tronchetti, *supra* note 5, at 223.

²⁴ *Compare* Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 4, at Art. I (omitting the term “exploitation”) with Moon Agreement, *supra* note 8, at Art. 11(5) (“international regime . . . to govern the exploitation of natural resources of the Moon.”)

²⁵ *Ibid.*

²⁶ Moon Agreement, *supra* note 8, at Art. 11(5) (emphasis added).

²⁷ *See* De Man, *supra* note 5, at 83-4 (arguing the lexical appearance of “exploitation” only in the Moon Agreement, not the Outer Space Treaty, is crucial for interpreting the latter through the former).

²⁸ *Ibid.* at 84-85.

form the Moon Agreement, Article 11(5) would outrun the Outer Space Treaty and consequently fail as the ceiling of the spectrum of possible interpretations.²⁹ Therefore, the Outer Space Treaty's term *use* must be wide enough to encompass commercial exploitation, subject to Article II and the benefits provision analyzed below.³⁰ Recent state practice confirms this functional reading. The United States and Luxembourg both premise private resource rights on the Outer Space Treaty's freedom of *use*.³¹ The Artemis Accords explicitly state in Section 10 that resource activities "shall be conducted under the auspices of, and consistent with, the Outer Space Treaty."³² None of these instruments attempts to amend Article I. They interpret *use* to include exploitation—exactly the move spectral interpretation predicts.³³

2.2. Defining Benefits

The term *benefit* remains undefined in Article I(1), but denotes something positive, useful, or profitable in ordinary parlance.³⁴ In practice, benefits may include scientific knowledge, raw materials, monetary profit, or technological advancements.³⁵ Nevertheless, what qualifies as a benefit may dramatically differ between states.³⁶ Raw lunar regolith may present immediate value to an industrialized state and little value to a state lacking the necessary processing infrastructure. This variability renders the benefits provision incredibly difficult to operationalize.

Despite the idiomatic nature of the term *benefits*, it untenable to read Article I(1) as allowing each state to dictate the exact benefits they receive.³⁷ Article I(1) by no means requires States to disgorge the entirety of their gains from a space activity.³⁸ Suggesting otherwise renders commercial exploitation endeavors into charitable enterprises. Certainly, forbidding exclusive rights to space benefits stanches development of infrastructure and slows humanity's enjoyment of resources.³⁹

Spectral interpretation buttresses this argument. The Moon Agreement supplies the interpretative ceiling by nearly repeating the Outer Space Treaty benefits provision verbatim⁴⁰ and further requiring the "equitable sharing" of "the benefits derived from" lunar "resources."⁴¹ The Outer Space Treaty, lacking the modifier, must impose a less prescriptive but still meaningful legal obligation. Accepted treaty

²⁹ *C.f.* Vienna Convention, *supra* note 11, at Art. 31(3)(c) (requiring interpretation in light of subsequent agreements) and De Man, *supra* note 4, at 84-5 (explaining subsequent instruments cannot expand obligations beyond the earlier treaty it elaborates). Nothing in the Moon Agreement purports to grant a right stand-alone of exploitation. Article 11(5) presumes that exploitation is already legal.

³⁰ De Man, *supra* note 5, at 84-85.

³¹ Commercial Space Launch Competitiveness Act, Public Law No. 114-90, § 51303, 129 Stat. 704, 720 (2015) (declaring U.S. nationals may obtain space resources "in accordance with applicable law, including the Outer Space Treaty"); Loi du 20 juillet 2017 relative à l'exploration et à l'utilisation des ressources de l'espace art. 2, 2017 Mém. A 674 (Lux.) (same premise).

³² Artemis Accords § 10 (Oct. 13, 2020) <https://www.nasa.gov/specials/artemis-accords/> (last visited Apr. 17, 2025).

³³ All instruments cite Outer Space Treaty Article I as their legal basis rather than proposing an amendment to the Treaty.

³⁴ Black's Law Dictionary. (2024). Benefit. In *Black's Law Dictionary* (12th ed). Thomson West.

³⁵ *Ibid.*

³⁶ Lee, R. J. (2012) *Law and Regulation of Commercial Mining of Minerals in Outer Space*. Springer, 156.

³⁷ *Ibid.* *E.g.*, Larson, *supra* note 17 at, 47 (describing the international recognition of remote sensing technology as a "universal benefit . . . even if the remote sensing occurred by commercial satellites").

³⁸ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 156.

³⁹ MacKay, M.A. (2020). Comment: Property Rights in Celestial Bodies: A Question of Pressing Concern. *Marquette Law Review*, 104(2), 575, 582.

⁴⁰ See De Man, *supra* note 4, at 44-5.

⁴¹ Moon Agreement, *supra* note 8, at Art. 11(7)(d).

interpretation methods affixes “the ordinary meaning” to words—meaning the term *benefits* should have a relatively similar meaning in both treaties regardless of the Moon Agreement’s requirement of equitable sharing.⁴² As such, Article I charges space actors with ensuring their activities yield benefits—tangible or intangible—available to all humankind while leaving each actor to choose an appropriate distribution mechanism.

3. BENEFITS PROVISION: AN ASPIRATION OR POSITIVE LEGAL OBLIGATION?

Building on the foundational analysis of Article I’s language, this section explores competing interpretations of the benefits provision and examines how commercial exploitation may—or may not—be deemed legal under the Outer Space Treaty. The restrictions on space activities enshrined by the Outer Space Treaty esteem space as an inclusive environment. Commercial activity—by its nature—tends to benefit a limited few. Article I(1) specifically requires all space actors carry out the use—or exploitation—and exploration of space for the benefit of all States.⁴³ This tension prompts a key question—does Article I(1) requirement permit commercial exploitation? The provision does not expressly prohibit commercial exploitation, but its meaning and legal force remain open to interpretation. Whether Article I(1) requires a diffuse and general benefit for all of humanity, tailored benefits gifted to each individual state, or something in between remains unclear.⁴⁴ The benefits provision fails to unequivocally ban commercial activity; however, the question remains as to whether any commercial activity successfully meets the requirements of Article I(1).⁴⁵

3.1. Potential Interpretations of the Benefits Provision

Facially, the benefits provision hinders commercial enterprise, especially if exclusivity is seen as incompatible with inclusivity.⁴⁶ At least three isolatable construals of Article I(1) exist that allow for commercial use of space.⁴⁷ Each construal reconciles exploitation with the benefits provision in different ways. These construals are also best understood along a spectrum of legal interpretation—displayed in

⁴² See Vienna Convention, *supra* note 10, at Art. 31(1).

⁴³ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 3, at Art. I(1). In full, the benefits requirement states that “exploration and use of outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies, shall be carried out for the benefit and in the interests of all countries, irrespective of their degree of economic or scientific development, and shall be the province of all mankind.” *Ibid.* Bohacek, P., et al. (2022). Benefit-Sharing as Investment Protection for Space Resource Utilization. *New Space*, 10(2), 127-135, 128 (reasoning that the Article I language indicates the existence of an obligatory sharing of benefits).

⁴⁴ Bohacek, et al., *supra* note 42, at 128. See also Lee, *supra* note 8, at 156. Recall, the Cold War encouraged treaty framers to write a treaty facilitating peace in space, not exploitation of space. Babcock, H.M. (2019). The Public Trust Doctrine, Outer Space, and the Global Commons: Time to Call Home ET. *Syracuse Law Review*, 69(2), 191-262, 206-07; Berkley, R. (1996). Space Law Versus Space Utilization: The Inhibition of Private Industry in Outer Space, *Wisconsin International Law Journal*, 15(2), 421-444, 421-22.

⁴⁵ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 184; Bohacek, et al., *supra* note 42, at 128 (“Article I of the OST . . . remains . . . the most unclear issue in the existing international space law regime”).

⁴⁶ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 160.

⁴⁷ *Ibid.* at 158. Lee uses the three construals to isolate the “possible outcomes and the corresponding applications on the exploration and extraction segments of a commercial space mining operation.” *Ibid.*

Figure 2—bounded by the Moon Agreement’s equity focused model at one extreme and a laissez-fair reading of the Outer Space Treaty at the other.

On the first construal, *the language holds an aspirational nature and imposes little to no legal obligation on sharing the benefits of space activities or exploitation of extracted resources.*⁴⁸ Should the language of Article I(1) only constitute a moral vision to guide space activities, it poses no obligation on exploiters to share the benefits of their space activities with non-space-faring States.⁴⁹ Thus, exploiters may share any

Figure 2

benefits voluntarily as they see fit. As well, conceiving of the benefits provision places little obligation on space actors to ensure the ability of others to conduct similar space activities. Perhaps, Article I(1) expresses a “future goal” that *eventually* imposes legal obligations.⁵⁰ Nevertheless, this construal of Article I(1) defines space as a generally unreserved domain in terms of legal obligation.⁵¹

On the second construal, *the language imposes a legal obligation on sharing the benefits of space activities but not on sharing the benefits from the exploitation of extracted resources.*⁵² Under this construal, Article I(1) only imposes an obligation on an exploiter to ensure exploitative activities do not preclude another’s ability to conduct similar activities.⁵³ Thus, this construal relies on a dichotomy between the act of exploiting the Moon and the later use of the benefits accrued from the act of exploitation.⁵⁴

On the third construal, *the language imposes a legal obligation on both sharing the benefits of space activities and the exploitation of extracted resources.*⁵⁵ Article I(1) imposing a positive legal obligation on

⁴⁸ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 158 (explaining the benefits provision as a “generalised mission statement rather than [a] positive and specific duty.”). *See also* Bohacek, et al., *supra* note 42, at 129 (describing the Building Blocks for the Development of an International Framework on Space Resource Activities “call for an actor to give ‘due regard’ to the interest of all countries and humankind, not calling for any mandatory or concrete fulfilment of the OST Article I”).

⁴⁹ Nevertheless, commercial exploitation provides a “positive development for all States.” Lee, *supra* note 8, at 158.

⁵⁰ Paxson, *supra* note 4, at 492.

⁵¹ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 158.

⁵² *Ibid.* Lee defines this as “no more than a negative duty of ensuring that the activity does not cause a detriment to any State.” *Ibid.*

⁵³ *Ibid.*

⁵⁴ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 158.

⁵⁵ *Ibid.* Contrasting from the previous construal, Lee describes this as a “positive duty to share the benefits from space activities.” *Ibid.*

both space activities and the sharing of space benefits precludes the exploiter from retaining the right to *all* benefits reaped from an exploited resource.⁵⁶ As the second construal relies on a dichotomy between the act of exploiting the Moon and the later use of the benefits accrued from the act of exploitation, this construal relies on the notion that the use of the reaped benefits still entails use of space.⁵⁷

3.2. *Exploitation for the Benefit and in the Interest of All?*

Among these interpretations, the third construal best aligns with the structure and intent of the Treaty. The construal conceives of the act of removing the resource and the act of deriving commercial benefit remain indelibly tied as uses of space.

First, the benefits provision appears in the operative body of the Treaty—not the preamble—granting it legal effect.⁵⁸ The first construal erroneously frames Article I(1) as a moral vision—one inappropriate for a treaty article.⁵⁹ Even though Article I(1) lacks a mechanism of self-execution because the Treaty fails to delineate the appropriate means to conduct space activities in a way that benefits all States, it carries the weight of a “duly formulated contractual norm.”⁶⁰ Thus, Article I(1) imparts a positive legal obligation despite the lack of an enforcement mechanism.⁶¹ In fact, the Moon Agreement serves as an attempt to provide a mechanism—albeit a weak one—to Article I(1).⁶² Despite its unacceptance as a method to enact the benefits requirement, the attempt to implement a method to fulfill the requirement suggests Article I(1) requires practical application.⁶³ Therefore, Article I(1) imposes a positive legal obligation beyond the simple moral vision.

Second, construal two demands a “dichotomy” between the *use of space* and the *use of space resources*.⁶⁴ The dichotomy insisted by construal two relies on the act of exploiting a space resource for economic gain occurs on Earth and not in space.⁶⁵ This dichotomy creates a host of issues in practice. To illustrate, advanced lunar mining endeavors feasibly require lunar bases powered by mined lunar materials, but this use of the mined materials constitutes an act of exploitation not occurring on Earth. Therefore, in this scenario, the dichotomy insisted upon by construal two fails because the act of reaping value from the resource remains entangled with conduct in space. The dichotomy requires tedious and senseless analysis to determine the difference between the *use of space* and the *use of space resources* for each space activity.⁶⁶ Thus, treating post-extraction use as beyond the scope of the Outer Space Treaty artificially narrows the reach of the benefits provision.

⁵⁶ Ibid; Vakaki, A. (2022). A New Gold Mining Rush?. *Journal of Space Law*, 46(2), 421-463, 452 (“[M]ining of space resources would be legal as long as it is for the benefit of all humankind, therefore it would not be in accordance with international space law if such mining is carried out only for exclusive interests.”). Although this interpretation strictly adheres to the text of the Outer Space Treaty, Vakaki recognizes the United States as forging an opposing legal interpretation that allows nationals to privately benefit from their space exploits. Ibid.

⁵⁷ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 181.

⁵⁸ Paxson, *supra* note 4, at 492.

⁵⁹ Ibid.

⁶⁰ Ibid; Bohacek, et al., *supra* note 42, at 128 (“considering Article I as purely inspirational whereas other articles of the OST are to be legally binding has been criticized by man legal scholars”).

⁶¹ Tronchetti, *supra* note 5, at 24-25.

⁶² Lee, *supra* note 8, at 157.

⁶³ Ibid. at 158.

⁶⁴ De Man, *supra* note 4m at 157. Note, De Man applies this dichotomy to Art. II rather than Art. I. Nevertheless, the dichotomy provides salient analysis to Art. I as well.

⁶⁵ Ibid. at 157-58.

⁶⁶ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 171.

Third, Article I(1) specifically identifies the plural *interests*, harkening “specific and identifiable interests” rather than a vague and all-encompassing singular *interest* solely applicable to humankind.⁶⁷ The singular *interest* implies a collective good where States possess a moral obligation to better humanity through space exploitation.⁶⁸ In opposition, the plural *interests* implies space actors must conduct their activities in a way that appeals to the individual interests or needs of each country.⁶⁹ Moreover, the plural *interests* reflect the reality that different countries carry different interests; thus, the Outer Space Treaty principles necessitate a tailored benefit sharing scheme that considers the interests of the benefits receiver.⁷⁰

3.3. *The Moon Agreement’s Perspective on Benefit Sharing*

Because the Moon Agreement “may arguably constitute the further elaborations . . . to give effect to the” benefits provision, spectral interpretation constitutes a sound means to demarcate the possible legal meanings of the benefits provision.⁷¹ Under the spectral interpretation theory, the Outer Space Treaty must impose a less restrictive benefit sharing obligation than the one identified in the Moon Agreement. Yet, this observation provides little clarity. The Moon Agreement implements the same benefits provision stated in Outer Space Treaty Article I(1) but further elaborates by requiring consideration of “present and future generations as well as the need to promote higher standards of living and conditions of economic and social progress.”⁷² Presumably, the Agreement’s Article 11(5) international regime bears the responsibility of determining the extent of the “equitable” benefit sharing requirements.⁷³ The Agreement further declares the moon and its resources “the common heritage of mankind,” a concept absent from the Outer Space Treaty.⁷⁴ Such language indicates a requirement of inclusive use through the sharing of the benefits reaped from those resources, and the Agreement leaves it up to “the international community,” not “individual States and their nationals” to define the scope of the benefit sharing legal obligation.⁷⁵ The exclusion of the common heritage concept from the Outer Space Treaty indicates that while the Treaty may also contain a benefit sharing requirement, individual states may possess the right to unilaterally determine the scope of that requirement as applied to their nationals.⁷⁶

The Outer Space Treaty lacks any stated requirement of equitable distribution, and the very rejection of the Moon Agreement emphasizes the Outer Space Treaty’s lack of an equitable sharing requirement reflective of the common heritage of mankind concept. Clearly, the Outer Space Treaty must lack the strong legal obligations to benefit sharing presented in the Moon Agreement. An undeniable distribution obligation still emerges under both treaties when a space venture produces a benefit worth sharing. Even so, a space mining venture accords with the Outer Space Treaty by sharing *something* with all other states that benefits all.⁷⁷ Nevertheless, the question remains as to *how much* and *what* must be shared for mining ventures to remain

⁶⁷ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 157 (citing Cheng, B. (1998). *Studies in International Space Law*. Oxford University Press, 234-35).

⁶⁸ *Ibid.*

⁶⁹ *Ibid.*

⁷⁰ *Ibid*; Bohacek, et al. *supra* note 42, at 132 (“each nation has different needs and interests, which eliminates the possibility of customizing the contribution to every single of them”).

⁷¹ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 157.

⁷² The Moon Agreement, *supra* note 8, at Art. 4.

⁷³ *Ibid.* at Art. 11(7).

⁷⁴ *Ibid.* at Art. 11(3).

⁷⁵ Goehring, J. (2021). Why Isn’t Outer Space a Global Commons? *National Security Law & Policy*, 11(573) 573-590, 579-80 (citing Cheng, B. (1998). *Studies in International Space Law*. Oxford University Press, 386).

⁷⁶ *Ibid.*

⁷⁷ Paxson, *supra* note 4, at 491 (“Article I imposes on nations binding obligations to share, even if these obligations remain ill-defined.”).

harmonious with Article I(1).⁷⁸ Despite these uncertainties, construal three provides a less stringent obligation compared to the Moon Agreement. By imposing a legal obligation on both sharing the benefits of space activities and the exploitation of extracted resources, construal three neither requires the Moon Agreement's governing regime nor the common heritage of mankind declaration. Having fixed the upper limit of benefit-sharing at the Moon Agreement's equitable-sharing clause, the analysis now turns to Article II's non-appropriation rule. The same spectrum applies: the Moon Agreement again provides the outermost ceiling, while a purely territorial reading forms the floor.

4. EXAMINING ARTICLE II OF THE OUTER SPACE TREATY

Spectral interpretation affirms that Article I of the Outer Space Treaty accommodates exploitation, yet a second hurdle remains in determining the legal obligations of space exploiters—the non-appropriation principle enshrined in Article II. Spectral interpretation treats an absence of regulation as the floor and the Moon Agreement's Article 11 as the ceiling. This Section locates lawful resource activities between these two poles. Our task is to locate lawful resource activities between these two poles. Where Article II remains silent, the Moon Agreement ceiling clarifies what remains prohibited and, by implication, permissible.

Read against the Moon Agreement, Article II restricts sovereignty and property claims—not resource extraction *per se*. Article II declares that “outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies, is not subject to national appropriation by claim of sovereignty, by means of use or occupation, or by any other means.”⁷⁹ Planting the U.S. flag on the lunar surface therefore conveyed no title to the land. The principle preserves the inclusive ethos that undergirds Article I's freedoms of access, exploration, and use. Determining the scope and effect of Article II requires the resolution of three main issues through spectral interpretation.⁸⁰ First, Article II expressly prohibits “national appropriation,” leaving the ability of non-national actors to appropriate unclear. Second, the phrase “by any other means” furnishes several competing interpretations of the definition of appropriation. Third, whether Article II applies to natural resources remains unclear. The Moon Agreement essential context and nuance for each inquiry.

4.1 To Whom Does the Ban Apply?

Although Article II speaks only of “national” appropriation, two treaty mechanisms extend the ban to private actors. First, interpreting Article II to private appropriation vacates the efficacy of the Outer Space Treaty as an insurer of space freedoms.⁸¹ Allowing private entity appropriation creates a legal loophole for states to appropriate space indirectly by owning a controlling share of a corporation, thereby eviscerating Article I's freedoms.⁸² Second, Article VI attributes “national activities . . . whether carried on by governmental or non-governmental entities” to the launching State and obliges it to authorize and continually supervise such activities.⁸³ Therefore, in public international law terms, the Outer Space Treaty

⁷⁸ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 3, at Art. I(1).

⁷⁹ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 3, at Art. II.

⁸⁰ See De Man, P. (2015-2016). The Exploitation of Asteroids and the Non-Appropriation Principle: Reflections on the Nature of Property Rights in Light of US Space Resources Act of 2015, 40(1-2), 1-55, 28 (discussing the controversy surrounding the legal scope of Article II).

⁸¹ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 4, at Art. I. Allowing an actor to claim ownership of an area in space inherently excludes another actor from using that area, violating the Outer Space Treaty's right to use and access all areas of space. *Ibid.*

⁸² *Ibid.*

⁸³ *Ibid.* at Art. VI.

converts private conduct into State responsibility.⁸⁴ Because State authorization is indispensable to sustain private property claims in space, any putative private appropriation necessarily violates the State's own obligations under Articles II and VI.⁸⁵ Therefore, if the state cannot appropriate the Moon, neither may its nationals because national approval—or lack of disapproval—of appropriative activities violates a state's obligations under Article IV.⁸⁶

4.2. What Types of Appropriation does Article II Concern?

The second problem concerns the types of appropriation included in Article II. Article II bans appropriation by claims of sovereignty, use, or occupation but omits enumeration of other methods to obtain exclusivity.⁸⁷ A strict reading might leave room for private real estate. The Moon Agreement clarifies the ceiling. Article 11(2) re-states the non-appropriation principle seen in the Outer Space Treaty, then in Article 11(3) iterates that “no State, international intergovernmental or non-governmental organization, national organization or non-governmental entity or . . . natural person” may claim the lunar surface or the “natural resources in place” as property.⁸⁸ If the Outer Space Treaty already forbade such property claims in Article II, then Article 11(3) would be “redundant.”⁸⁹ The presence of both articles signals that property qualifies as a subset of appropriation but does not necessarily qualify as co-extensive with appropriation.⁹⁰ Article II itself targets sovereignty claims and leaves property claims in a grey zone; under spectral interpretation, the Moon Agreement fixes the ceiling by outlawing property *in situ*, while allowing States latitude to regulate ownership of resources once removed from their natural context, provided Article I's benefit and Article II's non-sovereignty rules are respected.

4.3. What is the Physical Scope of Article II?

Neither the Outer Space Treaty nor the Moon Agreement defines the term *outer space*—leaving the physical scope of the non-appropriation principle ambiguous. Two interpretations exist: *sensu stricto* (the void between celestial bodies) and *sensu lato* (the void and matter contained therein).⁹¹ Article II states, “outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies, is not subject to national appropriation.”⁹² Both the Outer Space Treaty and the Moon Agreement fail to delineate what outer space constitutes, creating uncertainty.⁹³ Thus, should Article II only pertain to outer space *sensu stricto*, the ability to appropriate matter contained within outer space such as resources, relies on the definition of a celestial body because Article II specifies that outer space and celestial bodies are not subject to national appropriation.⁹⁴

Does the term *celestial body* capture all aggregate forms of matter in outer space, or does a celestial body have certain characteristics relevant to only certain arrangements of matter? Limiting a *celestial body* to a distinct class of objects renders the corporeal objects escaping this class appropriable—with the

⁸⁴ Cassese, Antonio. (2005). *International Law*. 2nd ed. Oxford University Press, 250; Tronchetti, *supra* note 5, at 30-31.

⁸⁵ Pop, V. (2009). *Who Owns the Moon? Extraterrestrial Aspects of Land and Mineral Resources*. Springer, 12.

⁸⁶ See Tronchetti, *supra* note 5, at 30.

⁸⁷ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 167

⁸⁸ Moon Agreement, *supra* note 8, at Art. 11(3).

⁸⁹ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 168.

⁹⁰ *Ibid.*

⁹¹ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 99-133.

⁹² Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 3, at Art. II.

⁹³ Epstein, D. (2024). Protecting the Cosmos: Defining Celestial Bodies in the Outer Space Treaty. *Space and Defense*, 15(1), 35-56, 36.

⁹⁴ *Ibid.*

understanding that these objects “are too insignificant to constitute celestial bodies, yet at the same time cannot be assimilated with outer space *sensu stricto* because of their material manifestation.”⁹⁵ Under this logic, delimitation of a celestial body occurs based on the ability of humans to remove the object from its natural location.⁹⁶ Consequently, movable objects serve as non-celestial bodies while immovable objects serve as celestial bodies.⁹⁷ Article II must pertain to outer space *sensu stricto*, not *sensu lato*.⁹⁸ Second, a third category of objects necessarily exists beyond outer space *sensu stricto* and celestial bodies.⁹⁹ The physical characteristics of these objects apparently exclude them from the class of celestial bodies which allows these objects to elude application of Article II.¹⁰⁰

The wording of Article II marks a textual shift from the UN General Assembly Resolution 1962’s conjunctive “outer space *and* celestial bodies,” signaling that Article II embraces space *sensu lato*, rendering smaller forms of aggregate matter.¹⁰¹ Any interpretation of *celestial bodies* and *outer space* demands applicability to the remaining provisions of the Outer Space Treaty.¹⁰² Excluding non-celestial body matter from application of Article II allows a significant portion of outer space to remain unregulated by space law, and the freedom to use and explore these non-celestial body (and non-outer space *sensu stricto* objects) would not be guaranteed by Article I.¹⁰³

No acceptable criteria exists to delimit the nondescript class of objects from celestial bodies or outer space.¹⁰⁴ Neither the Moon Agreement nor the Outer Space Treaty include a specific definition of the physical phenomena it purports to cover.¹⁰⁵ Regardless of any rendering of the term *celestial body*, the non-appropriation principle must indiscriminately applies to both outer space and the matter within space given Article II pertains to outer space *sensu lato*.¹⁰⁶ Thus, an inclusive approach avoids the ontological hair-splitting of trying to precisely define *celestial bodies*.¹⁰⁷ Any attempt to exclude certain collections of matter from the celestial body category results in an ambiguous legal regime.

4.4. The Moon Agreement and Non-Appropriation

The Moon Agreement better articulates the scope of its non-appropriation principle compared to the Outer Space Treaty by emphasizing the inability of any person or entity to claim sovereignty and the non-appropriable nature of lunar natural resources in place. Reading the Moon Agreement stipulation in Article 11(3) that no actor may claim the “natural resources in place” as property in conjunction with the Article 11(2) restatement of the Outer Space Treaty’s non-appropriation principle demonstrates that the Outer Space Treaty imposes no ban on the appropriation of natural resources in place.¹⁰⁸ Otherwise, no need exists

⁹⁵ Ibid at 132.

⁹⁶ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 189.

⁹⁷ Ibid.

⁹⁸ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 133.

⁹⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰⁰ Ibid.

¹⁰¹ Ibid.; United Nations General Assembly. (1963). Declaration of Legal Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space (Resolution 1962 (XVIII)) (emphasis added). De Man, *supra* note 4, at 133.

¹⁰² Ibid. at 134.

¹⁰³ Ibid.

¹⁰⁴ Ibid.

¹⁰⁵ Ibid. at 135.

¹⁰⁶ Ibid.

¹⁰⁷ Ibid.

¹⁰⁸ See Moon Agreement, *supra* note 8, at Art. 11(5)-(3).

for Article 11(3) because the restated language of the Outer Space Treaty would already capture a ban on the appropriation of natural resources in place. Accordingly, Article II occupies the lower band of the spectrum while the Moon Agreement’s non-appropriation clauses anchor the ceiling; every lawful resource project must thread that interval—eschewing sovereignty or in-situ property.

5. DEFINING NATURAL RESOURCES IN TERMS OF ARTICLE II

The previous section deems a deductive delimitation of outer space and celestial bodies to determine whether any legal basis exists for invidious application of Article II untenable considering the determination Article II refers to outer space *sensu lato*. Attempts to draw hard lines between space, celestial bodies, and natural resources proves doctrinally difficult. Article II’s inclusive phrasing appears hostile to exploitation because most extraction entails at least a minuet of *de facto* exclusivity.¹⁰⁹ To reconcile the tension, this Section proceeds with refining what counts as a resource without resurrecting the physical characteristics tests already rejected in Section 4.

The space law treaties make scant references to natural resources. In fact, the Outer Space Treaty makes no reference to natural resources. However, the Moon Agreement references natural resources by declaring “natural resources in place” not subject to ownership and by deeming the resources of the Moon “the common heritage of mankind” in Article 11(3) and Article 11(5).¹¹⁰ The *in-place* qualifier implies that removed materials exit the non-appropriation zone and become subject to the freedom to use and the benefits provision.¹¹¹ Likewise, the International Telecommunication Constitution labels radio frequencies associated with Earth orbit as “limited natural resources,” confirming that space resources may be both tangible or intangible.¹¹² The following paragraphs discuss potential interpretations orienting the non-appropriation principle to the legality of exploitation. *Figure 3* depicts these models.

Figure 3

¹⁰⁹ Epstein, *supra* note 92, at 40.

¹¹⁰ Moon Agreement, *supra* note 8, at Art. 11(3); Art. 11(5).

¹¹¹ De Man, *supra* note 4 at, 172. Further, Article 1(3) of the Moon Agreement states the agreement does not concern “extraterrestrial materials which reach the surface of the Earth by natural means.” Moon Agreement, *supra* note 8, at Art. 1(3).

¹¹² The ITU Constitution is almost universally ratified and adhered to. International Telecommunication Union. (1992). Constitution of the International Telecommunication Union, Art. 44(2)

5.1. Interpretation One: Article II Bans Appropriation of All Resources

Article II institutes an all-encompassing ban on the appropriation of any space resource—both tangible and intangible—because the language of the Outer Space Treaty makes no clear-cut distinction between outer space including celestial bodies and the natural resources therein.¹¹³ Therefore, Article II necessarily bans any exploitative acts entailing appropriation.¹¹⁴ Nevertheless, this interpretation contradicts the freedom to use space, enshrined in Article I, because it limits space actors from committing certain exploitative acts. Furthermore, this interpretation seems contrary to Article I(1) declaration that the use of space exists as the “province of mankind.”¹¹⁵

5.2. Interpretation Two: Article II Bans Appropriation of Movable Resources

Article II bans the appropriation of immovable resources by human intervention. Thus, movable resources may be legally appropriated because either they no longer serve as a part of “the constituent body” or the entire collection of matter may be captured and moved from its natural location.¹¹⁶ Consequently, these movable items cannot be considered celestial bodies or part of outer space *sensu stricto*. Thus, this interpretation falls prey to the same conundrum as the attempt to define celestial bodies based on their physical characteristics—an entire class of objects escapes the purview of space law. Furthermore, hinging the application of Article II on the ability to move matter renders Article II an empty shell because as technology develops, the ability to move more substantial collections of matter increases.¹¹⁷ Additionally, distinguishing between movables and immovables leaves several questions unanswered. For example, given the immovable nature of an orbital slot, the occupation of said slot by a satellite serves as appropriation.

5.3. Interpretation Three: Article II Bans Appropriation of Indivisible Resources

Like the movable versus immovable approach, but perhaps more tenable, framing resource exploitation through a dichotomy between the area and resource reframes the application of Article II.¹¹⁸ This dichotomy differs from the approach discussed in Interpretation Three by preventing the appropriation of entire bodies of matter, such as asteroids.¹¹⁹ This interpretation understands Article II as a ban on the appropriation of resources which represents an indivisible part of the territory to which the resource originates.¹²⁰ Thus, Article II serves as a prohibition of sovereignty over territorial areas. Indeed, exploitation of a natural resource fails to entail a claim of appropriation because the natural resource only serves as a component of the territorial body, and the integrity of the body does not rely on its components.¹²¹ For example, the area/resource dichotomy allows for the use of geostationary orbit because while a satellite occupies an orbital slot, the existence of the satellite entails no claim of sovereignty over

¹¹³ *Ibid.* at 151.

¹¹⁴ *Ibid.*; Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 3, at Art. II.

¹¹⁵ Lee, *supra* note 8, at 190.

¹¹⁶ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 153.

¹¹⁷ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 153 (citing Pritzsche, K.U. (1991). “Die Nutzung natürlicher Ressourcen” in Pritzsche, K.U. (E.d.) (1991). *Handbuch des Weltraumrechts*. Carl Heymanns, 567-68).

¹¹⁸ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 153.

¹¹⁹ *Ibid.* at 153; 157. See e.g., J. R. Brophy, et al. (2012). *Asteroid Retrieval Feasibility* [paper presentation]. 2012 IEEE Aerospace Conference, Big Sky, MT, United States (describing the scientific feasibility of forcing asteroid movement).

¹²⁰ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 153.

¹²¹ *Ibid.* at 179-206.

said area of space. However, the dichotomy between areas and resources presents an interpretation of Article II that does not rely on categorizing resources based on characteristics.

5.4. Exploitation based on Functionality

Interpretation three locates the lawful zone of exclusivity between Article II's territorial floor and the Moon Agreement's *in-situ* ceiling. To make that zone workable, this subsection adopts Philip De Man's "exploitation exponent" concept and calibrates it to the spectral framework.¹²² An exploitation exponent is any slice of outer space reality—material or immaterial—whose economic or scientific value can be realized only through a transformation that, for a limited time, demands exclusive control.¹²³ Exclusivity therefore stands as derivative, not constitutive—it inheres in the function the actor performs, not the territory from which the actor draws the exponent (or resource).¹²⁴

Article I already classifies exploitation as a lawful form of use; the resources territory of origin and the resource itself are merely "two overlapping states of the same physical matter" distinguishable solely on functional terms.¹²⁵ That freedom of use, however, does not lift the activity out of Article II's ambit—it simply means Article II cannot prohibit exclusive control, unless that control morphs into a sovereignty, property, or *de facto* claim.¹²⁶ A resource qualifies as an exploitation exponent the moment human intervention begins the transformation process—this could include digging, processing, and spectrum assignment. Vulnerability to exploitation, rather than physical traits like size or mobility defines a natural resource in space for legal purposes.¹²⁷ This encompasses both tangible and intangible assets and allows avoids fruitless debates about the status of a resource as a component of a celestial body or matter in outer space.¹²⁸

Because an exponent is defined by its transformation-linked value, the legality of excluding others hinges on whether exclusivity is *objectively necessary* to perform that transformation. Once the value is realized—or can be realized without exclusivity—the temporary right dissolves, preventing drift into permanent appropriation. Three treaty-based arguments establish such a distinction. First, characterizing exploitation in terms of both *use* and *appropriation* renders the Treaty self-defeating—an outcome the Vienna Convention repudiates.¹²⁹ Second, the Moon Agreement regulates exploitation in Article 11(5) and prohibits appropriation in Article 11(2), evidencing non-identity.¹³⁰ Third, the Outer Space Treaty contemplates exclusive control of lunar stations by permitting their existence.¹³¹ Exclusive use is thus not appropriation *per se*. The exploitation exponent doctrine operationalizes interpretation three without violating the Moon Agreement ceiling. It allows temporary, function bound exclusivity over severed resources while preserving Article II's absolute ban on sovereignty and property *in situ*.¹³² Exclusive rights

¹²² *Ibid.* See also McDougal, *supra* note 2, at 547.

¹²³ De man *supra* note 4, at 180-81

¹²⁴ *Ibid.*

¹²⁵ *Ibid.* at 181.

¹²⁶ *Ibid.* at 180 (arguing that the freedom of use permits temporary, function-bound exclusivity over resources, but such exclusivity must cease once it would amount to a sovereignty or property claim). See also Tronchetti, *supra* note 6, at 220-224 (distinguishing lawful exploitation from unlawful exploitation under Articles I and II).

¹²⁷ De Man, *supra* note 4, at 183.

¹²⁸ *Ibid.* See also De Man, P. (2011). The Commercial Exploitation of Outer Space and Celestial Bodies: A Functional Solution to the Natural Resource Challenge. *IAC-10-E71.4*, 28-38, 33 (defining intangible space resources).

¹²⁹ *Ibid.*

¹³⁰ Moon Agreement, *supra* note 8, at Art. 11

¹³¹ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 3, at Art. XII

¹³² De Man, *supra* note 4, at 184.

expire at their end of functional necessity—consistent with the inclusive ethos that threads Articles I and II together.

6. CONCLUSION: SPECTRAL INTERPRETATION

The Outer Space Treaty furnishes a thorny legal quandary. It grants all states the right to exploit space while simultaneously forbidding appropriation. Read in a vacuum, Articles I and II appear to conflict. Using a spectrum anchored by the subsequent Moon Agreement, however, resolves that tension into a coherent legal doctrine. Spectral interpretation treats the Moon Agreement as the outer ceiling of acceptable readings and the principles of the Outer Space Treaty as the floor. Between those anchors, a practicable middle band emerges. First, Article I imposes a positive but flexible obligation. Actors must ensure that the advantages of their space activities remain accessible to all humankind. Second, Article II bans sovereignty or lasting property in territory and in-situ resources, yet allows temporary, function-bound exclusivity over exploitation exponents. Third, because Article VI attributes private conduct to States, every extraction project ultimately remains a matter of public accountability, closing the loophole of corporate sovereignty by proxy.

Under this reading, the Outer Space Treaty permits space exploitation as long as actors avoid making territorial claims, prevent exclusive domains, and share resulting benefits in some form. The scheme preserves the Outer Space Treaty's inclusive ethos while offering industry a clear legal pathway. States can embed the exploitation exponent doctrine and the positive legal obligation from the benefits provision into licensing frameworks, and international bodies can issue non-binding guidelines to harmonize practice. Spectral interpretation reframes the Treaties—not as a paradox to be solved by future diplomacy, but as a mechanism capable of guiding responsible resource development. As humanity's presence in space expands, spectral interpretation will remain indispensable by ensuring the Outer Space Treaty ethos boldly governs the final frontier, even alongside the reality of commercial ambition.